

**SUSTAINABILITY IN ANCIENT INDIA: A COMPARATIVE
PERSPECTIVES OF ENVIRONMENT CONSERVATION IN
BRAHMINIC, BUDDHIST AND ISLAMIC PERIOD**

***Indrajit Mahato & **Dr. Mazhar Shamsi Ansary**

Abstract:

Education is the backbone of a nation because of playing an important role in order to build important carrier so that social change could be brought since ancient times. Environment education is an important topic in any society of a country. Environment education teaches that there is a need to maintain a balance between the flora and the fauna. For which human beings as conscious beings need to acquire sufficient knowledge about environment education. The three most popular education systems in ancient India were Brahminic, Buddhist and Islamic. Although these education systems were based on their religion in some forms or others, their content and style of teaching were impeccable. These education systems were one of the institutions of quality education. Environmental studies were included along with other subjects in the curriculum and was practiced accordingly. This article will focus to discuss in detail about this particular topic based on qualitative approach following an analysis of secondary data.

Keywords: Sustainability, Environment Education, Flora and Fauna, Brahminic Education System, Buddhist Education System and Islamic education system.

** Visiting Lecturer, Department of Education, Mahatma Gandhi College, ** Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Netaji Nagar College for Women*

Introduction:

The progress of a society or a country depends on the quality of education. Content required for interacting with the changing environment is included in the curriculum of specific countries. The present age is the age of technology. Therefore, technology is included in the curriculum of the current education system. Many such subjects are included in the syllabus as per the need and other subjects are included in the syllabus when the need arises. But there are some topics that have a unique place in the curriculum all day. It is as important today as it was in the past, and it is to be hoped that these issues will increase in the future. One such subject is Environment Education. As the days go by the relationship between nature and man is getting severed. Human beings have a responsibility to keep their environment healthy and a unique branch of this environment is nature. And because of the misuse of these natural resources, the environment is losing its prosperity (Shende, 2015). World Environment Day has been declared on the 5th of June every year to make people aware of this (Tanwar, 2016).

Various initiatives have been taken by the government to protect the

environment. Such as Wildlife Protection Act (1972), Wildlife Protection Rules (1973), Forest Conservation Act (1980), Biological Diversity Act (2002) etc. (Prabhu, 2018). The United Nations has also introduced the concept of sustainable development to protect the environment (Morton and et al, 2017). The purpose of all this is to maintain a balance in the environment.

At present the government has taken various initiatives to protect the environment but, in the past, there was no need to adopt any special rules or regulations. Only the students' curriculum included various activities related to the environment and in that the students were quite aware of the environment. If we look at the education system of ancient India, we can see that even in those days people were quite conscious about the environment. Environmental science took place in the curriculum of Brahmanical education system, Buddhist education system, Islamic education system and so on. Although there were differences in the ideology of these three education systems in other respects, but in all education systems, environmental studies were given considerable importance and space was given in the curriculum.

We are solely responsible for the situation we are currently in. Disorders such as global warming, COVID-19, etc. have been created due to neglect of environment. So, people need to learn from the education system of the past just as they are aware of the need to protect the environment now.

With this brief introduction let us peep into the objectives and the research questions of this article.

Objectives:

1.To unlock the activities on environment conservation during Brahmanical period.

2.To reveal several activities on environment conservation during Buddhist period.

3.To identify the activities on environment conservation during Islamic period.

Research Questions:

1.What are the activities on environment conservation during Brahmanical period?

2.How environment conservation activities were conducted during Buddhist period?

3.What are the activities on environment conservation during Islamic period?

Methodology:

This is a totally theoretical investigation. A qualitative approach is to be applied in this study. This study is based on secondary source. Various books, articles, books written by various resource person on these education systems (Brahminic, Buddhist and Islamic) are used as a secondary data.

Discussion:

Objectives No. 1: To know the activities regarding environment conservation during Brahmanical period.

One of the most regulated education systems in ancient India is the Brahminic education system. This education system was a carrier of the fusion of Indian culture and Aryan culture (Pal, 2021). This education system is one of the examples of environment education which was given much importance even in the ancient education system. The system of Brahminic education was mainly Hindu centered on the Vedas. The specific aims of the education system, the curriculum, the teaching methods, the educational institutions, the rules and regulations in which environment

education has repeatedly emerged as follows:

Sacredness of Nature:

The Brahminic education system was basically Vedic. And in the Vedas, various deities were given importance. Vedas and Upanishads are giving emphasizes on “Pancha Maha Bhutas” (earth, water, fire, air and space). Indra (God of rain and thunder), Varuna (water), Agni (fire), Pusan (cattle) etc. These elements of nature are essential for a healthy environment. These elements were given special importance in Brahminic education system (Bithin, 2019). In the Rigveda too we can see sun, tress, rain gods are worshipped. The educational institution of that era was one of the examples of the practice of environment education. Under a lonely big tree, the teachers used to share their knowledge with their students. As a result, students could better understand the environment. One of the notable things is that in Atharvaveda, it embarked on hymn for forests, curing herbs, and water conservation (Nayak, 2019).

Environmental Ethics:

Environment education was also involved in the daily activities of celibates. For example, collection of wood during ‘Yajna’ (Kanojia, 2024). As we know that it

is the symbol of ecological balance. As a result, we may notice a pattern of planting trees. Also had to involve in drinking water collection, rearing etc. The concept of ‘Rita’ that is cosmic order; it is maintaining the balance between nature and human (Harshit, 2025).

Practical Conservation:

The Vedas were included in the syllabus of Brahmin children. So, they had to follow the activities mentioned in the Vedas. For example, the conservation and nurturing of plants, animals and human beings. Forest conservation and development have been compared to mother, friends and God (Bhattacharya, 2014). At that time, environment education was directly involved in the curriculum of the of Shudra community among the four castes. Since they had no right to study, the modern concept of curriculum, i.e. life-centered curriculum, included agriculture, animal husbandry etc. By which they would have the opportunity to interact directly with the environment (Sonowal, 2009).

Objectives No. 2: To understand several activities regarding environment conservation during Buddhist period

After the Brahminic education system, the other ancient education system

that gained popularity was the Buddhist education system. In response to the Brahminic education system and religion, the Buddhist education system or religion was born (Masih & Vidyapati, 2018). Yet some features of the Brahminic education system were observed in the Buddhist education system. Just as nature and environment were emphasized in the Brahminic education system, the same pattern was maintained in the Buddhist education system. The following are the cases in which the practice of nature and environment was observed in the Buddhist education system.

Philosophy of Non-violence (Ahimsa):

In Buddhist scriptures, Buddha mentions the word '*Sigalovadasutta*' for using natural resources without jeopardizing the nature. For example, a bee collects honey without damaging the flower. As a result, natural resources will not run out in the future. The tree has been given special importance in Buddhist scriptures. And the Buddhist education system was based on the Buddhist scriptures (Vajira, 2018). The Buddhist scriptures say that "*rukko nama pupphaphaladharo..... rukko upagatanamanuppa vitthanam jananam chayam deti, rukko chayavemattam na*

karoti". That is, man and nature depend on each other. So, man needs to build a healthy relationship with nature and its elements. Tripitaka has been included in the curriculum of Buddhist education system as a subject of education. In Vinay Pitaka, where it is said to follow the words of Buddha and Buddha has given importance to nature and environment among other things in his scriptures (Bala & Gill, 2019).

Environmental Practices:

In the Buddhist education system, students were taught in a noise-free place. Because Buddhist monks believed that in a quiet and noise-free environment, students develop their mental state and self-awareness.

- The word '*Dhamma*' is used in Buddhist scriptures. By which man has been told to obey the laws of nature. Humans have been told to use minimum of natural resources, which will allow mankind to use natural resources till death. There are many similarities between the concept of sustainable development and the concept of Buddhist philosophy and education.

- Pancasila has been mentioned in Buddhism and philosophy. In the first of these five *śila*, it is suggested to develop a compassionate and empathetic attitude

towards the flora and fauna. Killing an animal and eating its meat is strictly forbidden. These rules and regulations had to be strictly adhered to by the students studying in Buddhist monasteries.

- Environmental pollution is strictly forbidden in Buddhism and Buddhist scriptures. Trying to keep water, air, rivers, etc. clean. At the same time, various rules and regulations were made to keep the environment around oneself clean and tidy.

- Various Buddhist monks have made various statements to create a caring and sympathetic attitude towards the environment and nature. Which had to be complied with by those contemporary students. Showing love for the environment and nature, the eminent Buddhist monk Maha Ghosananda said, 'When we respect the environment, the nature will be good for us. When our hearts are good, then the sky will be good for us. The trees are like our mother and father, they feed us, nourish us and provide us with everything, the fruit, the leaves, the branches, the trunk. They give us food and satisfy many of our needs. So, we spread the Dharma of protecting ourselves and protecting our environment, which is the Dharma of the Buddha.' (Singh, 2015)

Objectives No. 3: To identify the activities of environment conservation during Islamic period

In order to baptize people in any religion, the education system of that religion is needed. That is why Islamic education system was developed centering on Islam. The word of Allah is the Quran and as the messenger of Allah, from time immemorial various Islamic great men have conveyed the word of Allah to the common people. According to Islam, the first messenger of Allah is Adam and the last messenger is Muhammad (Douglass & Shaikh, 2004). Islamic education system was formed following the words of Islamic great men and Islamic education system gained popularity at that time by various educational institutions. For example, Maktab for primary education, Madrasah for secondary education etc. were established (Pareek, 2015). The following is a discussion of how these institutions practiced environment education, along with other teachings according to Islam.

Islamic view of Nature:

According to Quran Hadith and Khalifa's, they also stressed that all mankind are trustees of Earth. It largely emphasizes on water conservations, tree planting

(gardens) and moderation of resource uses (Chaudhry, 2022). It is mentioned in the Quran that everything on earth is created from water and the owner of this earth is Allah himself. Humans have been created to protect primary resources and other species will enjoy these natural resources. These principles had to be followed by the students (Salem and et al, 2012). In Islam, animals and plants are divided into two parts. One group that lives its own right, the other group that plays an important role in serving the people and the development of the world. So, if mean unjustly oppresses these animals or plants, then in the court of Allah that animals or plant will complain against the human race and say "So-and-so killed me for no purpose." So Islamic students had to be careful about the environment and nature (Gada, 2014). The Holy Quran and Sunnah guide us towards sustainable development in our Islamic countries as well as throughout the world. Simultaneously, environmentally harmful activities such as industrial pollution and reckless exploitation are termed as environmental corruption (Zafar, 2024).

"And do good as Allah has been good to you. And do not seek to cause corruption

in the earth. Allah does not love the corrupters," (Surah Al-Qasas 28:77).

Unfortunately, there are many Muslims who fail to protect the environment and develop environmental awareness from an Islamic perspective, that is why the Holy Quran repeatedly reminds us: 'O children of Adam! Eat and drink, but do not waste. Surely, He does not like the wasteful,' (Ahmed & Rahman, 2025). Damage to nature and environment has been seen as a sin in Islam. Because Allah wants to create a unity between man and nature, and natural resources have a right not only to the present species but also to future generations. That is why the destruction of nature and environment is called 'Fasad' in Islam.

Environmental Conservation Practices and Architecture in India:

In the mediaeval period, all Mughal emperors are focusing on 'Charbhagh systems' which promoted conservations of gardens which denotes harmony with nature. In the 'Babarnama' (Babar's memoir), it also pressing light on 'Flora and Fauna' and stressing its preservations (Minhaj, 2008). In the Akbar's era, he encouraged regulated hunting and afforestation. In the Tughlaqi era, Firoz Shah Tughlaq promotes

tree plantations, established so many canals and reservoirs. As we know that Mughal emperors are very much strong in architectures. In this architecture, integrated water tanks, cooling systems and gardens showing that the harmony with ecology. As an example, Shalimar Bagh in Kashmir, which is a blended form of ecological planning plus aesthetics (Managt Socio Human, 2023).

Conclusion:

Among the educational systems of ancient India, these three types of education (Brahminic, Buddhist and Islamic education system) have undoubtedly paved the way for a new path in the education system of modern India. It is impossible to find such a well-planned education system anywhere else in the world as India. At a time when natural resources are being depleted, global warming, epidemics like COVID-19 are all round, the technologically advanced modern man has found time to look at nature and the environment. It goes without saying that Brahminic, Buddhist and Islamic education systems included various activities to balance the environment. In Hinduism, Buddhism and Islam, harming the environment was seen as a sin. Again, these three types of education were based on their

respective religions. So, people spontaneously participated in protecting the environment. Students will do doubt be aware of the environment if similar activities of the past are included in the current education system. The good relations between man and nature that existed in the past will continue to develop today and at the same time the epidemics that occur as a natural disaster will come to an end.

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